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AGEMERA: Integrating Non-Invasive Geophysical Technologies, AI, and Social Strategies for Sustainable Critical Raw Material Exploration in Europe

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The AGEMERA project (*Agile Exploration and Geo-Modelling for European Critical Raw Materials*), funded under the Horizon Europe programme and recognised as a *Horizon Europe Technology Success Story* (European Commission: European Health and Digital Executive Agency, 2024), supports the EU's green and digital transitions by addressing challenges in the supply of critical raw materials (CRMs) (European Commission, 2024).

AGEMERA advances CRM exploration by integrating geological, technological, and social strategies. It enhances understanding of mineral deposit models through systematic research approaches, including data collection, synthesis, and modelling. By refining mineral system models, AGEMERA aims to identify overlooked CRM deposits and promote sustainable mining practises in the EU (Holma et al., 2022)

From a technological perspective, AGEMERA employs non-invasive methods such as muography, ambient noise seismology (Romero and Schimmel, 2018), and drone-based electromagnetic surveys (Pirttijärvi et al., 2014) to minimise environmental and societal impacts. These methodologies are supported by the AGEMERA AI engine, a cloud-based platform that integrates diverse datasets through AI Knowledge Packs (Štimac Tumara and Matselyukh, 2024). The platform facilitates efficient data processing, targeting, and visualisation via a natural language interface.

The project emphasizes social local (non)acceptance and the integration of community perspectives in mining practices through tools like surveys and participatory methods. Educational initiatives, including university courses, public events, and an online game, aim to increase

awareness of CRMs' societal importance and encourage responsible resource management.

Key deliverables include:

- Enhanced models for CRM exploration.
- Non-invasive geophysical methodologies.
- AI-driven data integration platforms.
- Tools to evaluate and address community acceptance of mining.
- Educational resources to support sustainability awareness.

Aligned with the EU's Critical Raw Materials Act (European Commission, 2024), AGEMERA promotes sustainable CRM supply chains and reduces reliance on imports. By integrating geological, technological, and societal dimensions, AGEMERA contributes to Europe's transition to a low-carbon, circular economy.

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